

DC motor speed control with an AC-DC converter

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Abstract— In this experiment, we use an AC-DC conversion to regulate a DC motor's speed. In order to regulate DC voltage for applications such as battery charging and DC motor drive, a suggested AC-DC converter has been made. The AC to DC converter has a unidirectional design. For the DC-DC buck converter, a feedback control system built on the PWM methodology has been developed. It regulates the output to control the speed of the DC motor. A PWM controller regulates the output generated by the DC-DC converter. The pulses are produced by the Arduino microcontroller. The period of duty of the pulses should be changed for controlling the DC motor's speed. Software called MATLAB/Simulink is used to simulate the suggested system.

Keywords— PWM controller, DC motor, AC-DC converter, and Buck converter, Regulator, Power factor.

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of single phase ac to dc conversion systems is growing daily in tandem with the growing demand for dc power. The majority of applications need a dc supply with a voltage between 9 and 400 volts. Consequently, having an effective power conversion system is essential. This unidirectional ac to dc converter design is intended to control a dc motor's speed. An apparatus that revolves and transforms power from electricity into mechanical energy is known as a motor. A circuit that switches a source of direct current among voltage ranges referred to as an electronic circuit. Different types of DC-DC converters exist, such as buck, boost, buck-boost, and cuk converters, among others. It is necessary to regulate the speed of the DC motor coming out of the DC-DC buck converter. The buck converter's output is controlled by the PWM approach. An Arduino microcontroller is used to create pulses. It is necessary to regulate the buck converter's output in order to control the pulses' duty cycle. Numerous control techniques, including as fuzzy logic control, sliding mode control, adaptive control, and predictive control, might improve the performance of the feedback control system. However, because of its simplicity, we are employing the PWM approach in this paper. A DC motor's speed and supply voltage are often directly related. In this article, the output of the control system based on PWM technique utilising Arduino microcontroller is implemented in order to address the issues mentioned above regarding controlling the speed of DC motor. This, in comparison to linear control approaches, minimises power loss by lowering heat dissipation and harmonics or ripples in the rectifier's output. The transistor used to regulate the motor is either fully on or off.

SYSTEM DISCRIPTION

The constructed system can be seen in fig. 1 below.

Fig-1 Block representation of the basic conversion process

The AC-DC converter is supplied with a single phase, 230V AC power source. The AC-DC converter functions as a buck converter and rectifier in a unidirectional manner. PWM converters use Arduino microcontrollers to generate pulses. The AC-DC converter's output receives the pulses that are produced. Additionally, the converter's output serves as a control load to regulate the DC motor's speed.

Below is the AC-DC converter circuit diagram:

Fig.2:-Circuit diagram of AC-DC converter

This single phase supply, which has been frequently employed in many earlier designs, is provided to the rectifier to convert the AC input from the main supply to DC. In order to minimise the number of diodes, the ac source is supplied to a half-controlled AC-DC converter and coupled with the buck converter structure. It is composed of two switches, Q1 and Q2, two diodes, D1 and D2, an output capacitor, C, and a resistive load, R. There is just one inductor, L. The rectifier is not affected by switching frequency because it operates at power frequency, or 50 Hz. By adding a capacitor to the rectifier's output, the ripple in the conversion's output is reduced.

Mode-1

Fig.3:- Mode 1 circuit diagram

The positive process has the first two modes, and the negative cycle has the next two. This has Q1 and D1 running, the inductor L charging, and the load voltage as stated below:

$$V_{out} = V_{in} - V_L$$

Mode-2

Fig.4:-Mode 2 circuit diagram

Here, Q1 is off, Q2 and D1 are running, the inductor L is discharging, and the load voltage is as follows:
 $V_{out} = V_L$

Mode-3

Fig.5:-Mode 3 circuit diagram

In this, Q2 and D2 are running, the inductor L is being charged, and the voltage of the load is as follows:
 $V_{out} = V_{in} - V_L$.

Mode-4

Fig.6:-Mode 4 circuit diagram

In this, Q2 is off, Q1 and D2 are running, the inductor L is discharging, and the voltage of the load is as follows:
 $V_{out} = V_L$.

II. SIMULATION SETTING UP AND OUTCOME

The proposed converter's simulation settings are

Table 1

Parameter/Components	Ratings
Frequency	50Hz
Input voltage	35V
Load resistance	60Ω
MOSFET switches	Ron=0.001Ω, Rd=0.01Ω
Capacitors	220μF
Switching frequency	5KW
Inductor	1.96mH
Output voltage	9-24V

Simulation circuit for ac-dc converter is given below:

In the simulation model, a 35V input supply will be supplied to the rectifier. The rectifier's output is connected to the buck converter. The high voltage is stepped down to a lower one via the buck converter. The AC-DC converter produces 9–24V DC as its output. Furthermore, the motor load has been replaced in the simulation model with a resistance equal to the motor load.

The following is a simulation circuit for an AC-DC conversion:

Fig 7:-Circuit for complete conversion system

This works by connecting a diode rectifier—which transforms AC voltage into DC voltage—to an AC source that is 35 V and 50 Hz. This results in an increase in power electronic switches but a decrease in diodes. The converter may function within the range of 9V to 24V output voltage by providing an alternative reference voltage of 9V or 24V. The load is linked with a 60 ohm load resistance. Figure 8 presents the load voltage as well as reference voltage for the specified arrangement.

Fig 8:-Load voltage with reference voltage

The real load voltage (yellow line), which is 2.08% of the reference voltage (blue curve), is followed by the load voltage ripple, which is approximately 0.5V. Figure 9 shows the estimated system's power factor.

Fig 9:-Power factor of proposed system is around 0.98

Fig 10:- Voltage and current output as well to power

The output voltage, current, and power are displayed in the figure that follows. Peak load voltage is approximately 23.9V, peak current is 0.41A, and peak power is 9.8W. The output results' waveforms are displayed in Fig. 10 above.

III. CONCLUSIONS

In this project, we'll be using an AC-DC converter to regulate a DC motor's speed. The modes of functioning of the proposed converter are analysed. By altering the duty cycle, the PWM approach produces an output voltage that is widely variable. Table I lists the necessary components, reduces the size of the converter, and minimises the number of switches. The primary benefits and uses of this suggested AC-DC converter are that it has few switches, which means that losses will be minimal. During simulation work, the converter receives an input of 35V and outputs 24V. In this case, the R load is 60Ω and the power factor is measured as 0.98.

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